

THE MAIN DIFFERENCES OF APHORISMS FROM OTHER TERMS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5905512>

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Аннотация: В этой статье будут рассматриваться особенности афоризмов как законченной мысли. А также отличительные и схожие признаки афоризмов в сравнении с парадоксами, эпиграммами, каламбурами и крылатыми выражениями.

Ключевые слова: парадоксы, эпиграммы, каламбуры, крылатые выражения.

Annotation: This article will consider the features of aphorisms as a complete thought. As well as distinctive and similar signs of aphorisms in comparison with paradoxes, epigrams, puns and winged expressions.

Key words: paradox, epigrams, puns, winged words.

If we bring together the main definitions of the concept of "aphorism", then it can be defined as a dictum (belonging to a famous author or an anonymous one), in which the complete thought of the directive (instructive) or declarative (constitutive) character, mainly socially significant topics, deep and at the same time often witty or even paradoxical content.

In the most general sense (based on the criteria found in all or most of the existing definitions), an aphorism is a short statement in the form of a complete statement, in which a generalized thought of theoretically (or practically) meaningful content is expressed. This understanding of aphorism allows not only to outline its boundaries as statements of a certain type (speech genre), but also to differentiate the aphorism in the circle of speech and linguistic units adjacent to it¹.

Paradox and aphorism

The paradox, according to the established definitions, is an original, at odds with the generally accepted, and often with common sense, judgment. The concept of paradox arose in ancient philosophy to denote a

¹ Иванов Е.Е. Лингвистика афоризма. Могилев. МГУ имени Кулешова. 2016, 34 с.

new, unusual opinion. The paradox was also widely used in rhetoric, the outstanding orator of antiquity Cicero dedicated his philosophical work "Paradoxes" to him. Paradoxes add brilliance to statements, attract unexpected conclusions and are taken as evidence of independence and intelligence.

The paradox as an independent one should be distinguished from the stylistic *prima* - paradoxicality. The property of paradox has long been considered one of the artistic means of language and is considered among the rhetorical figures. And if the paradox - an opinion that contradicts the generally accepted one - is far from aphorism, then paradox, - a form of paradox, often given to the truth to draw attention to it - is quite often found in aphorism.

The paradox is often based on hyperbole, bringing exaggeration to incredible proportions and distorting reality.

Since the main property of paradoxes is their disagreement with generally accepted opinions, the determination of the truth of the thoughts contained in them entirely depends on the worldview and class attitudes adopted in society. In this regard, some judgments in one society can be attributed to paradoxes, and in another - to aphorisms that affirm the truth.

The paradox differs from the aphorism in a radical way. In paradoxes, in the first place is the striving for unusualness, novelty, originality, and not for the truth. For aphorisms, the striving for the truth of thought is always in the first place, and it is possible to distinguish them from paradoxes only by the truthfulness of the judgment.

In essence, in aphorism and paradox, most of the genre features - literary origin, laconicism, completeness and brilliance of judgment - coincide, with the exception of the main feature - the truth of thought. The aphorism seeks the truth, affirming the eternal, humane principles of life, while the paradox seeks to attract attention, surprise, amaze with its unusualness, without caring about the truthfulness of thought².

Epigrams and aphorisms

An epigram, in the interpretation accepted in our time, is a satirical poetic miniature ridiculing a person or phenomenon. The epigram has been known since ancient times. Having arisen in ancient Greek poetry in connection with the production of inscriptions on monuments, it did not have modern typical features. The themes of the ancient epigrams were very versatile: religious, initiatory, love, drinking, sometimes satirical. Many epigrams were of a moral and philosophical nature and did not differ in any

² Манн Т. Сочинения/Т. Манн., Т.2. – М., 1958, 289 с.

way from sayings. Only later did the ancient Roman poets Catullus and Martial give the epigram a predominantly satirical look, and in this form it has come down to our times.

What is the difference and what is the similarity between epigrams and aphorisms? The similarity is that both of those of book origin have brevity, accuracy and completeness of judgment. The difference between epigrams and aphorisms, first of all, is that they usually represent a poetic satirical miniature, while aphorisms tend to prose and do not always contain satire.

An epigram is often created “on occasion”, and, unlike aphorism, it is always specific and does not touch on abstract, “eternal” issues that are at the center of the aphorism's attention. An epigram most often carries a new thought, not always of a wide scale, but usually relevant for a given moment. The aphorism, on the other hand, represents a wise thought, not necessarily a new one, but only enclosed in an original form.

The enumeration of the specific features of the epigrams seems at first glance to be quite sufficient to distinguish them from aphorisms. However, in practice this is not entirely true. In collections of epigrams, poets sometimes include epigrams on moral and philosophical topics, devoid of satire, which can be attributed to aphorisms.

The aphorism is a product of generalization and is aimed at a dialectical consideration of the order of things. The epigram notes the properties of individual characters and phenomena typical for a given time. In the aphorism, the true opinion of the author is more clearly revealed, which is facilitated by the inherent direct meaning of the presentation. The epigram often does not give an idea of the author's position and is often allegorical. In a simplified comparison, we can say that the epigram is more fun and cunning, and the aphorism is more serious and profound³.

Pun and aphorisms

A pun is a play on words based on the use of homonyms, homographs, comic etymologization of words and other techniques aimed at giving a thought a special expressiveness and comic effect. The pun is widely used in satire, in particular in epigrams, as well as in the comedy genre.

Puns have been known since ancient times, for example, they were often found in the epigrams of Marcial, and later in the comedy works of W. Shakespeare.

³ Новиков. – М.: Книга. Русская эпиграмма/Сост., вступ. ст. и примеч. 1986, 258 с.

Puns make thoughts expressive, poignant and entertaining. And quite often this seemingly entertaining form of presenting thoughts contains serious and wise judgments.

Winged words and aphorisms

The definitions of the concept "winged word" according to literary data are not contradictory, as in the case of the word "aphorism", but they do not have concreteness. According to them, the winged word is some kind of collective term that combines apt expressions, literary quotes, sayings of historical figures, common aphorisms. However, if you turn to the collections of winged words, you can find that neither sayings nor aphorisms are found in them, but they consist of apt, very short, well-known expressions of literary origin. The name of the word "winged" comes from Homer, who in his poems "Iliad" and "Odyssey" called the words that break from the mouth of the speaker and "fly over" directly to the listener. This word was used as a literary term only at the end of the 19th century after the publication of the book by the German scientist G. Büchmann "Winged Words" (1864)⁴. In Russian, this term began to be used after the publication in 1890 of S. V. Maksimov's book "Wing Words", containing his own somewhat expanded interpretations of these words.

It is clearly seen from the examples given that the winged word, unlike aphorisms, does not have a complete inference. It is more of a concept than a judgment. An aphorism is always equivalent to sentences, a catchword is often equivalent to words.

Winged words do not evoke thought and act on consciousness only in close union with their ancestry. This feature of winged words determines their obligatory wide distribution, their mass reproducibility. If an aphorism, even one that has just appeared, is always understandable, then the word becomes "winged" only after widespread publicity, when people are well aware of the conditions for its occurrence.

The winged word should be considered an independent literary term that has nothing to do with aphorism. It differs from aphorism in the absence of a semantic inference in that it has multiple meanings of use and often a figurative meaning⁵.

Overall, for aphorisms with comparing to paradoxes, the striving for the truth of thought is always in the first place. In a comparison with the epigrams, the aphorism is more serious and profound. If to compare aphorisms with puns then puns quite often entertaining form of presenting

⁴ Büchmann G. "Winged Words" 1864, 79 с.

⁵ Энциклопедический словарь/изд. Ф.А. Брокгауз, И.А. Ефрон. СПб., 1898, 680 с.

thoughts contains serious and wise judgments. The main differences winged words from aphorisms in the absence of a semantic inference in that it has multiple meanings of use and often a figurative meaning.

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